
Integrated Approach to Biogas Production Using Cow Dung Enhanced with Poultry Waste as an Additive Factor

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ABSTRACT

The sustainable utilization of animal waste, particularly cow dung and poultry droppings, offers significant potential for renewable energy generation. This study investigates the effect of incorporating poultry waste into cow dung substrates on biogas yield, as well as the influence of pH under controlled anaerobic digestion conditions. Substrates were prepared using a simple dry-processing method, and five digester setups were constructed using locally sourced materials modeled after a floating-drum system. Gas production was monitored daily at 14:00 h for ten days. Among the five experimental setups, the mixture containing cow dung and poultry waste in a 2:1 ratio (set-up 2) produced the highest biogas volume (89 cm³), representing approximately 2-fold, 1.1-fold, 1.4-fold, and 1.6-fold increases compared with set-ups 1, 3, 4, and 5, respectively. Increasing the poultry-waste content beyond this ratio resulted in a decrease in biogas yield, indicating an optimal threshold for co-digestion. Throughout the research, digester pH (6.5–8.0) and mesophilic temperature (20–40 °C) were maintained within recommended ranges for effective anaerobic digestion. The findings demonstrate that a 2:1 cow-dung-to-poultry-waste ratio offers an efficient, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly substrate blend for enhanced biogas production.

Keywords: Biogas, anaerobic digestion, cow dung, poultry waste, co-digestion.

1.0 Introduction

The rising global demand for energy, coupled with the progressive depletion of fossil fuel reserves, poses a major challenge to industrial expansion and economic development in countries such as Nigeria. Fossil fuel resources, particularly petroleum are finite in quantity and will inevitably decline over time (Ogunwande et al., 2013). Consequently, renewable energy alternatives hold increasing importance for long-term energy security.

Although renewable sources such as solar, wind, and hydro power are promising, their deployment requires significant financial investment and technical capacity, which remain major constraints for many developing nations (Ahmadu, 2009). Biogas technology, however, presents a relatively low-cost, environmentally friendly, and scalable option. Methane (CH₄), the principal component of biogas, has a global warming potential 21 times greater than that of carbon dioxide (CO₂). Its controlled combustion, therefore, reduces greenhouse impact while providing useful energy. The residual digestate from biogas systems also serves as a valuable organic fertilizer and assists in managing municipal waste and reducing pathogenic organisms.

Nigeria is endowed with abundant renewable and non-renewable energy resources, including biomass, but the country's energy sector continues to struggle with inefficiency and supply inadequacy (Iwayemi, 2008). Biogas generation from organic waste particularly animal waste presents a dual advantage of providing alternative energy while improving environmental sanitation (Karki et al., 2005).

Previous studies have investigated biogas production from cow dung, poultry droppings, and other organic residues, including co-digestion processes (Nnabuchi et al., 2012). Despite these efforts, reported biogas yields remain relatively low, and challenges persist regarding optimal substrate composition and pH management (Alfa et al., 2014).

The present research, therefore, examines the effect of varying proportions of poultry waste as a co-substrate with cow dung, as well as the corresponding influence of pH on biogas generation using five experimental setups.

2.0 Materials and Method

2.1 Materials

Cow dung and poultry waste were sourced from the Kofar Na'isa Livestock Market and Dansalo Farms respectively, all located at Kofar Na'isa quarters, Kano. Each material was sun-dried, pulverized, and stored as a substrate. A digital weighing balance was used to measure substrate quantities. A 5-litre plastic container served as the digester, fitted with a rubber cork sealed with grease to prevent gas leakage. A 250ml measuring cylinder functioned as the gas collector, connected to the digester through a rubber hose. The system followed the fixed-drum digester model.

2.2 Method

The digesters were constructed following a modified version of Karki's biogas model (Karki, 2005). For set-up 1, 40g of cow dung was mixed with water in a 1:3 ratio to form a slurry, which was introduced into the digester. The digester was stirred daily before measurements were taken. Temperature, pH, and gas volume were recorded at 14:00h for ten consecutive days.

The same procedure was applied to the following substrate combinations:

- **Set-up 2:** 40g cow dung + 20g poultry waste

- **Set-up 3:** 40g cow dung + 40g poultry waste
- **Set-up 4:** 40g cow dung + 60g poultry waste
- **Set-up 5:** 40g cow dung + 80g poultry waste

Biogas production was determined by downward displacement of water, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1. Experimental set up

2.2.1 Determination of Moisture Content (MC)

Moisture content was calculated following the method of Hassan, (2015):

$$\% MC (dry wt) = \frac{a-b}{a} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where:

- a = initial sample weight
- b = weight after oven-drying
- $(a - b)$ = moisture lost.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Biogas Production

Set-up 2 produced the highest biogas volume (89 cm³), representing approximately:

- **2-fold** increase compared with Set-up 1
- **1.1-fold** increase compared with Set-up 3
- **1.4-fold** increase compared with Set-up 4
- **1.6-fold** increase compared with Set-up 5

These results indicate that the inclusion of poultry waste significantly enhances biogas yield up to an optimal point, beyond which additional poultry waste reduces efficiency. The observed performance aligns with findings from previous studies emphasizing the suitability of poultry waste as a co-substrate (Nnabuchi et al., 2012; Alfa et al., 2014).

Figure 2. The cumulative gas volumes for all five setups.

3.2 pH Variation

Figure 3. The pH trends over digestion period.

Optimal pH values for anaerobic digestion typically range between 6.5 and 8.0 (Rahman & Mueeed, 2010). All experimental setups fell within or close to this range, with values between 7.0 and 8.0. Set-up 1 displayed a slightly expanded range (7.1–9.5), likely due to internal aerobic activity in the absence of poultry waste. Maintaining pH within the optimal range is essential for microbial activity and methane formation (Fasoyin, 2019).

3.3 Temperature Variation

Figure 4. The average temperature across setups.

Ambient temperature remained between 26°C and 29°C throughout the experiment. This range falls within mesophilic conditions (25–40°C), which are suitable for stable anaerobic digestion and microbial activity. All setups operated within this favorable temperature zone.

4.0 Conclusion

This study demonstrates a simple, cost-effective, and locally adaptable approach to biogas production using cow dung and poultry waste. Among the five substrate combinations tested, the 2:1 cow-dung-to-poultry-waste ratio (set-up 2) produced the highest biogas yield (89cm³). Increasing the proportion of poultry waste beyond this ratio reduced gas production. Optimal operational conditions were achieved with pH values between 7.1 and 7.6 and temperatures between 26°C and 29°C.

These findings highlight the potential of co-digestion as a practical strategy for improving biogas yield in Nigeria. For optimal biogas production, the proportion of cow dung should be approximately double that of poultry waste.

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